

DEVELOPMENT OF THE CULTURE OF PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION IN ENGLISH OF STUDENTS OF THE PHARMACEUTICAL HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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Abstract In this article, we define the importance of strong communication and discuss seven tips to help you improve your communication skills.

Key words: communication and discuss, workplace, Clear expectations, Discovering.

Аннотация В этой статье мы определяем важность эффективного общения и обсуждаем семь советов, которые помогут вам улучшить свои коммуникативные навыки.

Ключевые слова: общение и обсуждение, рабочее место, четкие ожидания, открытие.

Communication is a valuable soft skill for the workplace, whether you're working in the office or exchanging messages over an instant messaging app. Competent communication enables you to collaborate with your coworkers, deliver instructions for work assignments and take responsibility for your professional conduct. Aiming to become better at communication can enhance your work performance and your reputation in your industry.

Communication skills can impact the relationships that you build in the workplace. Here's a list of reasons that illustrate why practicing effective communication is important:

Clear expectations

When spearheading a project, communication is a tool you can use to establish clear expectations for every member of your team. You can discuss why the project is important to the company and the results you're anticipating from the team's hard work. Clarifying your thoughts can help professionals understand their role in the group and what they can do to ensure that the project is successful.

Collaboration with coworkers

As a part of a team, you can prioritize good communication with your coworkers. Knowing how to express yourself can allow you to share your expertise to contribute to the team's workflow. You can also resolve interpersonal conflict and foster trust to make collaboration easier and more productive. For example, if you're working with a coworker who's new to the company, you can talk about the department's policies and approaches to projects. Your coworker may appreciate that you're upfront about how to complete the assignment and you're dedicated to showing them how to be successful.

Career opportunities

Improving your communication skills can also help you advance your career. You can impress prospective employers with your ability to articulate your thoughts, engage them in a conversation and build strong professional relationships. As a strong communicator, you can connect with experts in your industry who may be willing to speak on your behalf to representatives of companies that are hiring. Any communication, whether to an employee, co-worker or customer, should clearly convey the intended message to the intended recipient.

It must be easy to understand and straightforward without ambiguity. Unclear communication with multiple interpretations is confusing and may give the receiver the wrong idea, which can result in lost productivity and profit in the business setting. Often the aim of communication, especially business communication, is to elicit a response. Carefully worded communication making it easy for the receiver to respond will achieve this. The words used and the tone of the communication play a significant role in getting the desired response. The response may be positive, neutral, or negative and conveyed through words or actions. Effective business communication aims to forge and enhance relationships with both employees and customers. It should build credibility and make the receiver feel positive about the sender and the organization. Communication that creates trust and positivity will aid future business success. Correctly executed, this communication goal fosters effective teamwork and loyal customers. One of the goals of business communication is reaching employees and customers in the most effective way possible. Technology is constantly advancing, providing new and exciting ways to educate, inform and engage them. Experimenting with different media to deliver engaging information is an effective communication goal. A company's purpose is its reason for existence and should be communicated in a simple, relatable way to all stakeholders. Sharing your mission and values helps the receiver create a deeper connection and care more about the organization. Consistently communicating your purpose helps motivate and inspire employees. Understanding and feeling part of the company's purpose instills pride and gives meaning to their day-to-day tasks. If your communication goal is to change behavior then reinforcement with repeat information is an effective communication strategy. It often takes seven or more interactions with your brand before a prospective customer engages with you. If you want to see a positive change in employee behavior a single message will not suffice. Repeat communication, using every possible channel will reinforce the message, allow it to sink in, and over time result in behavior change.

Record yourself communicating

Whether working on a group project, giving a speech or simply just speaking with others, record a few communications and evaluate opportunities for improvement. Discovering where you can improve is a good first step to establishing a baseline for skill development. Pay attention to the pronunciation and enunciation of your words and the pace at which you speak to determine if it's easy for your audience to understand you. Identify the areas that you feel you're proficient at and the areas that you want to target as you aim to enhance your communication.

Improve your listening skills

Besides speaking, a successful conversation in a work setting involves listening and responding. Practice active listening, a technique that requires you to use verbal and nonverbal techniques to hear and interpret what your conversational partner is saying. Paraphrase what they say to show you're paying attention to the discussion. Your responses can also incorporate your interpretation of what they say to propel the conversation forward.

Learn to manage your emotions

Good communicators build skills that help them control their reactions and react appropriately. Learning how to communicate with others means learning more about yourself and your own emotional development. Think about subjects you're passionate and sensitive

about so you maintain your composure when speaking with someone. Your emotional intelligence can also refer to your ability to identify emotions in others. When you broach a new subject or respond to a question, observe your audience's reaction so you know how they feel about your speech patterns.

Improve your nonverbal communication

Non-verbal communication is important to understand what you and other people might be conveying beyond words. Pay attention to someone's body language and facial expressions and listen to their tone. What they're saying and what they're doing could be conveying different things. Eye contact is also an important part of nonverbal communication. Doing something as simple as making eye contact while speaking and listening can help maintain your focus on the conversation.

Be receptive to feedback

When speaking, pay attention to both verbal and nonverbal feedback. If your coworker says they don't understand something, provide more explanation to answer their questions and educate them on the topic. If they're nodding their heads, then you can conclude they agree with your assessment and are curious about what else you have to say. Receptiveness to your audience's feedback accentuates your adaptability skills, and you can make sure the conversation you're leading is productive.

Goodwill and branding

The best way to convey communications such as invitations, seasonal greetings, thank-you letters, congratulatory messages and condolences is in writing. Personalized written messages help develop positive and respectful professional relationships. You can also use letters to promote customer relationships, create a positive impression and build goodwill. You might send a professional contact a written letter, for example, for their birthday, when their son or daughter gets married or when they receive a promotion.

Written business letters make these situations more personal and promote friendship. For this reason, they are indirect business promotion tools.

Besides communicating information and building goodwill, letters also help create a positive image of the company that sends them. Every letter a company sends is a goodwill ambassador that speaks for the organization's values and quality.

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